

Original papers

Prediction performance of portable near infrared reflectance instruments using preprocessed dried, ground forage samples

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ABSTRACT

Forage analysis by near infrared reflectance (NIR) spectroscopy has had many advancements since it began in the 1970s. There have been steady improvements in instrumentation, in computers, and chemometric algorithms for developing calibrations. Thus, making NIR the most used technique to routinely analyze samples for forage producers, plant breeders, animal nutritionists, cattle farmers, and feed companies. This study compared the performance of prediction across three different portable instruments compared to a bench top laboratory NIR instrument, using a wide range of alfalfa and grass preprocessed dried, ground forage samples. Laboratory instrument scans were replicated with a reduced spectral range to match the range of each portable instrument. Alfalfa tended to have better calibration and test-set statistics than the grasses in this study. Portable instruments evaluated did not scan the upper portion of the spectral range (1652–2498 nm), which had some negative impact on forage calibration. The SCiO instrument scanned a very narrow range (740–1070 nm); and, although it had comparable results to the laboratory instrument constrained to same wavelength range, most major peaks related to forage quality traits are outside this range. The expensive bench top laboratory instrument had the best performance as expected, while the very inexpensive SCiO portable instrument had much greater error of prediction to the point that, for most traits, the prediction would not be considered reliable. However, the AuroraNir and the NIR-S-G1 digital light processing portable NIR may provide an alternative to expensive bench top laboratory equipment while still providing sufficiently accurate predictions. Therefore, some portable instruments have the potential to be used for on-farm analysis of wet, coarsely chopped forage, and this option must be evaluated in future studies.

1. Introduction

Forage analysis by near infrared reflectance (NIR) spectroscopy has come a long way since Norris et al (1976) published the first attempt at using NIR on forage crops. From that milestone, almost 50 years ago, there have been continuous improvements in instrumentation, computers, and chemometric algorithms for developing calibrations. Thus, making NIR the most used technique to analyze routine samples for forage producers, plant breeders animal nutritionists, cattle farmers, and feed companies. Initially NIR spectroscopy was used to evaluate protein content of grains and forages (Chen et al., 2013). Currently the

technology is used for a wide range of animal feed components (Paz et al., 2019) and it has become the standard analytical method for routine analysis in the feed industry.

In the dairy industry, nutritionists heavily rely on NIR spectroscopy for determining the nutritional profile of hays and silages in order to optimize dairy ration. Forages are a major dairy diet component with large variability in composition coming from small hay lots produced by the farmer and their composition may change over time (St-Pierre and Cobanov, 2007; St-Pierre and Weiss, 2015; Weiss et al., 2012). Also, the latest nutritional forage analysis profiles from commercial labs include *in vitro* digestibility measured at different time of incubation, which

Abbreviations: PLS, Partial Least Square; SECV, Standard Error of Cross Validation; RSQcv, R² in cross validation; SEL, Standard Error of Laboratory measurement; RPD, Ratio of Performance to Deviation; RPDcv, RPD in cross validation; RPDval, RPD predicting test set; r2val, r2 predicting test set; SEP, Standard Error of Prediction.

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requires weeks of analytical work at an extremely high cost. In turn, this is making NIR spectroscopy the analytical technique most used for routine forage analysis. Typically, samples are shipped to a laboratory and they are dried and ground (preprocessed) to reduce them into a fine homogeneous powder before being scanned by an NIR instrument. Because of this intrinsic variability it is necessary to sample and analyze them on a regular schedule with the need of receiving the analytical results in a short period of time; as silages in bunker cannot be pre-sampled and hay lots may be consumed quickly as they arrive at the farm (St-Pierre and Cobanov, 2007).

Despite the diffusion of these instruments and the advancements in electronics, bench top instruments remain quite expensive and their use is limited to a controlled laboratory environment. Beside the improvements of lab bench instruments, there has been a quick development of miniaturized NIR sensors with a variety of different technologies used to separate wavelength within the NIR spectral range (Yan and Siesler, 2018). There are sensors based on diode array equipped with diffraction grating or in recent years using a linear variable filter (Viavi Micronir, San Jose, CA, USA). Another solution is based on Digital Light Processing (DLP) technology developed by Texas Instruments (Dallas, TX, USA) which is also adopted in video projectors that uses a single detector. The other class of sensors are represented by miniaturized interferometers acquiring Fourier-Transform NIR spectra based on single-chip Michelson interferometer (Si-WareSystems, Cairo, Egypt) or Fabry-Perot interferometers (Spectral Engine, Helsinki, Finland).

These technology advancements created in the last 15–20 years have allowed development of miniaturized spectrometers with commercialization of portable or pocket size instruments. These instruments may be less sensitive to environmental challenges, such as temperature variation, vibrations, or presence of dust. These portable instruments can be directly attached to agriculture equipment, or for field on-farm analysis. Interest in these new portable spectrometers is supported by the increasing number of applications in many different fields to include feed, food, and pharmaceutical uses (Bec et al., 2020). Portable NIR instrumentation may offer the opportunity to scan and analyze samples without any preprocessing in the future, but the goal of this study was to evaluate forage samples normally prepared under laboratory conditions and compare performance to a traditional bench top instrument.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples and reference analysis

A total of 612 alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.) and 516 grass samples were used in this study. The sample sets were compiled from eight alfalfa and grass experiments in 2015, 2016 or 2017 at sites in central, western and northern New York, USA (Table 1). These studies were part of a forage management research program conducted by J.H. Cherney (Cornell University, Ithaca, NY, USA). The eight experiments were completely independent of each other with all conducted at different field sites over different years. Ten alfalfa cultivars were included, along with 16 grass cultivars from six grass species: tall fescue (2) [*Lolium arundinaceum*

Table 1
List of agronomic studies and number of samples.

Trial no.	Study	Year		Alfalfa, n.	Grasses, n.
15–45	1	2015	Calibration	100	94
15–85	2	2015	Calibration	40	33
16–67	3	2016	Test-set	88	54
16–69	4	2016	Test-set	63	63
16–91	5	2016	Calibration	83	83
16–92	6	2016	Calibration	52	60
17–68	7	2017	Calibration	60	48
17–93	8	2017	Calibration	126	81
Total				612	516

(Schreb.) S.J. Darbyshire], meadow fescue (6) [*Schedonorus pratensis* (Huds.) P. Beauv.; syn. *Festuca pratensis* Huds.; syn. *Lolium pratense* (Huds.) Darbysh.], orchardgrass (4) (*Dactylis glomerata* L.), Festulolium (2) (Festulolium Asch. & Graetn.), reed canarygrass (1) (*Phalaris arundinacea* L.), and timothy (1) (*Phleum pratense* L.). Depending on the goals of each study, alfalfa and grass were in either pure or mixed stands, with samples collected from early spring to late fall. Forage samples were hand-harvested with a battery-powered clipper from an approximately 0.25 m² area that varied depending on stage of growth, at a 10-cm stubble height from all plots for nutritive value determinations. Samples from mixed alfalfa-grass plots were separated into pure alfalfa and grass components for analysis. All samples were dried in forced-air ovens to a constant weight at 60 °C, and ground in a Wiley mill (Thomas Scientific, Swedesboro, NJ) to pass a 1-mm sieve and placed in labelled sealable plastic cups.

Samples were analyzed using wet chemistry procedures described by Valentine et al. (2019), using sodium sulfite in the neutral detergent solution. Forages were weighed into ANKOM F57 filter bags (ANKOM Technology, Macedon, New York, USA) for amylase treated neutral detergent fiber (aNDF), acid detergent fiber (ADF), acid detergent lignin (ADL) and 48 h *in vitro* digestibility (IVTD) analyses. Neutral detergent fiber digestibility (NDFD) was calculated as the proportion of the total fiber digested, expressed on an aNDF basis. Nitrogen was determined using a combustion process (LECO CN628 analyzer, DairyOne, Ithaca, NY) and crude protein was calculated as N × 6.25 (AOAC, 1995). Based on duplicate analyses, the laboratory standard error (SEL) was calculated (Table 2) for each nutrient (Fearn, 2005) as:

$$SEL = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n d_i^2}$$

with d = difference between duplicates and n = number of samples in the evaluation. Correlations among nutrients within each forage type were calculated using SAS add-in for Excel v7.15 (SAS, 2017).

2.2. NIR spectra collection

Four different spectrometers (Fig. 1) were used (Table 2): 1) Foss NIRSystem 6500 [Foss North America, MN (LAB)]; 2) AuroraNir [Grainit s.r.l., Italy (DA)]; 3) NIR-S-G1 [Innospectra, Taiwan (DLP)]; 4) SCiO [Consumer Physics, Israel (SW)].

2.2.1. Sampling process for DA and SW

Ground samples were thoroughly mixed and 2 to 3 g were transferred in a conical pile in a plastic container (55 × 130 mm, 25 mm height) that also served as a cap to cover the DA lens to prevent external light from entering the device during internal standard scanning. The DA was fitted into the cap, compressing and flattening the sample pile. After taking the first scan with the DA, the instrument was carefully removed to avoid disturbing the flattened sample pile and the SW with an optical shade attached was held over the sample with the optical shade in contact with the sample. After scanning with the SW, sample was returned to the original sample container and then transferred again to a conical pile in the plastic container for a second scan using both instruments. The sample was returned to the sample container and transferred to the plastic container again for a third SW scan. The DA was used to flatten and compress the sample pile and a third scan was obtained with the SW, resulting in duplicate DA scans and three SW scans per sample. For every sample, prior to the first DA scan, the lens was covered and an internal reference scan was run. Prior to using the SW each day the internal calibration program was run with the lens covered. Scans for DA and SW were collected at Cornell University Forage Analysis Laboratory by J.H. Cherney (Ithaca, NY, USA).

Table 2
Instruments and their characteristics.

Instrument	Technology	Spectral range, data point	Sample scanning	Scan Area	Number of scans
FOSS NIRSystem 6500	Pre-dispersive Scanning monochromator	400–2498, 1050	Rotating quartz cuvette	72 mm ² (24 × 3 mm)	32 scans
AuroraNir	Post dispersive Diode array	950–1650, 256	Contact	130 mm ² (10 × 13 mm)	2 scans of 2 s (approximately 200 spectra)
NIR-S-G1	Digital light Processing (DLP)	950–1650, 400	Contact	11 mm ² (Φ 3.8 mm)	10 scans of 3 s (approximately 50 spectra)
SCiO	unknown	740–1070, 12	Contact	Estimated 54 mm ² (6 × 9 mm)	3 scans

Fig. 1. Average alfalfa spectrum using four different instruments. LAB = Foss NIRSystem 6500; DA = Grainit s.r.l. AuroraNir; DLP = Innospectra NIR-S-G1; and SW = Consumer Physics SCiO.

2.2.2. Sampling process for LAB and DLP

Samples within plastic cups were shipped to the US Dairy Forage Research Center (Madison, WI, USA) where scans for LAB and DLP were collected. For the LAB instrument, samples were fitted in a ring cuvette (50 mm diameter) with optical quartz. The instrument was equipped

with an autosampler and set for 16 scans of the reference followed by 32 scans of the cup while spinning. For comparison, all DA, DLP and SW were stationary scans. For DLP sampling, samples were deposited on a cardboard surface and flatted using a spatula. Samples were scanned at 10 different spots, slightly moving the DLP after each spot scan covering different areas of the sample surface. An external reflectance reference was used at the beginning of each DLP scanning session and repeated approximately every 30 min.

2.3. Calibration development and statistics

For all instruments, repeated scans were averaged to obtain only one spectrum per sample. All spectra were either recorded or transformed in absorbance as log 1/R using Unscrambler X (Camo, Norway), interpolated if necessary (DLP and SW) at every 2 nm and imported in UCAL 4.0 (Unity Scientific, Brookfield, CT, USA) software that was used for all calculation and calibration development. Spectra were assembled into two databases, one for alfalfa and one for grasses, and each spectrum was matched to the wet chemistry of the same sample.

LAB had the full spectral range from the visible (400 nm) to the upper NIR range (2498 nm), encompassing the spectral range of the other three instruments (Fig. 2). To make comparisons within the same spectral range, the LAB database was replicated with a reduced spectral range (1100–2498 nm) typical of instruments used in commercial laboratories (LABT). Spectra were trimmed to the same range (950–1650 nm) of DA and DLP (LABD), and reduced to the infrared wavelength range of SW (740–1070 nm) (LABS).

Before developing any calibrations, datasets were cleaned of possible

Fig. 2. Average alfalfa spectrum using four different instruments. LAB = Foss NIRSystem 6500; DA = Grainit s.r.l. AuroraNir; DLP = Innospectra NIR-S-G1; and SW = Consumer Physics SCiO.

spectral outliers. For this reason, PLS calibration were developed using LAB database and chemistry value, with t-values [$t = \text{absolute (NIR - Wet chem)}/\text{Standard error of Calibration}$] above 2.5 removed from the database. Calibrations were developed using a partial least square algorithm (UCAL 4.0, Unity Scientific, Brookfield, CT, USA) using the same mathematical treatment for all databases for all instruments. Spectra were pretreated using standard normal variate and detrend (Barnes et al., 1989) as scatter correction followed by first derivative, calculated between four datapoints and smoothing over four datapoints. There was no outlier elimination as databases were previously cleaned from outliers and all instruments were tested with exactly the same database. Maximum number of PLS principal components was set at 15, but actual number were optimized using a four-groups cross-validation process.

To test the relative performance of different instruments, the database was split into a calibration set (Studies 1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 8; Table 1) and a test-set (Studies 3 and 4; Table 1). Calibration models were then applied to the test-set datasets. Calibration performance was evaluated based on the standard error of cross validation (SECV), r^2 of the PLS model (RSQcv), and on the test-set statistics including standard error of prediction (SEP), r^2 (r^2_{val}), bias and slope; all calculated by UCAL(Unity Scientific, Brookfield, CT, USA) software. In addition, other performance indicators were calculated including the ratio of performance to deviation (RPD) calculated either as the standard deviation of the reference data divided by SECV (RPDcv), or divided by SEP (RPDval) (Williams, 2014).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Wet chemistry data

One of the major requirements necessary to evaluate performance of NIR instruments and calibration is to quantify SEL of the primary methods used to build calibrations (Williams et al. 2017). Calculation of SEL of simple nutrients is well defined (Fearn, 2005), but may be complicated for NDFD which is determined by sequentially applying *in vitro* digestion followed by NDF determination. Since there is no relationship between NDF duplicate 1 and IVTD duplicate 1, NDF duplicate 1 was randomly paired with either IVTD duplicate 1 or 2 when calculating NDFD for each sample, prior to calculating SEL. This randomization process was repeated on the entire data set 10 times, with an average SEL for NDFD due to different pairing between runs of IVTD and NDF is quite small ($SD = 0.0303$, $n = 10$), and in Table 3 is shown the overall SEL for NDFD.

Tables 4 and 5 contain statistics for calibration and test-set for alfalfa and grass samples. There are differences between the number of samples across variables in the database This is because databases were cleaned by removing outliers before calibration development. Criteria to eliminate chemistry values were based on the difference between wet chemistry and NIR predicted values, evaluated using the entire (Calibration + Test-set) LAB instrument database. On average, removal of outliers for both forages was very limited, as it was less than 2%, which is quite acceptable for NIR calibrations (Williams et al., 2017).

Even though test-set samples were from different studies the composition between calibration and test-set data sets were quite similar

Table 3
Laboratory standard error for wet chemistry of alfalfa and grass.

Parameter	SEL, %DM	n
Crude protein	0.210	56
Acid detergent fiber	0.737	112
Neutral detergent fiber	0.447	112
Acid detergent lignin	0.349	112
In vitro true digestibility (48 h)	0.568	112
Neutral detergent fiber digestibility	1.340	112

SEL = Standard error of laboratory.

for range, average and standard deviation (Tables 4 and 5). Having included different source of variations (multiple cultivars, multiple grass species, range in maturity, growing seasons and years) both forages showed large variation in composition which is desirable when developing NIR calibrations as it represents a larger portion of the product variation (Esteve Agelet and Hurburgh, 2010). If compared to values of alfalfa and grass hays from uncontrolled source like in commercial laboratories (Dairyland Laboratories, 2020). The samples of this study showed on average a better quality indicated by a greater CP and NDFD value and lower aNDF concentration for both forages. Tables 4 and 5 include the maximum r^2 obtainable based on the SD and SEL of each parameter (Williams et al., 2017). Except for NDFD, the maximum r^2 obtainable was always above 0.9 with a value of 1 for CP.

All constituents were significantly ($P < 0.05$) correlated with each other for both forages, with correlation between fiber fractions (aNDF, ADF, ADL, IVTD and NDFD) of 0.73 or higher in absolute value (Tables 6 and 7). The correlation between CP and the other traits had values of 0.42 or greater in absolute value, but were all statistically significant. The relatively high correlations most likely reflected differences in plant maturity that include changes in leaf: stem ratio and cell wall structure that affect all constituents similarly (Ball et al., 2001), with the exception of CP concentration having a somewhat weaker relationship to morphology and cell wall development.

3.2. Spectral data

The LAB instrument spectra span from 400 to 2498 nm covering the spectral range from visible (400–740 nm) to the shorter NIR range (702–1100 nm) typical of low cost silicon detectors, but also included the longer NIR range (1102–2498 nm) typical of InGaAs and PbS detectors. This large spectral range can be covered only by using two type of detectors in the LAB instrument. This range overlaps the spectral range of the other three instruments (Fig. 1), comparing the average spectrum of alfalfa for the 4 different instruments. Spectra of the different instruments compared to LAB showed a similar shape within their own ranges, but with some offset having greater (SW) or lower (DA and DLP) absorbance.

Despite some fairly large differences in absorbance the correlation between LAB and other instrument spectra was (0.996, 0.982 and 0.997) for DA, DLP and SW, respectively. Correlation between DA and DLP was the lowest at 0.973. The high correlation between LAB and SW was unexpected considering that SW has only 12 photodiodes (Sparkfun Website, 2020) compared to the scanning monochromator of LAB. Visually the 700–1100 nm range of SW did not show any particular peak, but with just slight bends in spectra. This is, in contrast to the upper part of the NIR range from 1100 to 2500 nm with LAB which clearly shows many peaks and bends that can be attributed to a variety of absorbing molecules like water, protein, lipids and carbohydrate. The range 700–1100 nm is defined as the third overtone spectral region (Workman, 1996) that has a much lower absorption coefficient than the first and second overtone including the combination band region in the range 1100–2500 nm.

3.3. Calibration performance

3.3.1. Laboratory instrument

There are many indicators (Tables 8 and 9) that describe calibration performance, but this discussion will focus on SECV, RPDcv, SEP and the relationship between SECV and laboratory analytical errors. Also, LABT was considered the reference instrument as it is *de facto* the standard in the forage analytical industry.

For alfalfa (Table 8), LABT showed RPDcv values above 3 with the only exception of NDFD. Using Williams (2014) evaluation of performance, RPDcv for IVTD would be classified as “Good”, “Very Good” for ADL and “Excellent” for NDF, ADF and CP. Values of RPDcv have a direct link to R^2 as $RPDcv = 1/\sqrt{(1-RSQcv)}$ and the same classification can be

Table 4
Chemical composition statistics for Alfalfa calibration (n = 461) and test-set (n = 151).

Set	N	Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Mode	Median	RSQ MAX
CAL	456	CP, %DM	24.76	3.84	17.47	35.31	19.83	24.22	1.00
	451	aNDF, %DM	31.39	5.27	20.52	44.25	32.97	32.25	0.99
	452	ADF, %DM	25.15	4.9	15.35	36.41	18.79	25.11	0.99
	449	ADL, %DM	5.18	1.2	2.86	8.17	3.57	5.18	0.91
	457	IVTD, %DM	84.73	4.84	72.4	94.57	81.12	84.5	0.98
	453	NDFD, %aNDF	52.47	8.85	30.93	78.88	46.57	51.76	0.94
VAL	151	CP, %DM	23.11	3.77	15.4	30.82	17.53	23.77	1.00
	151	aNDF, %DM	30.96	5.58	21.32	44.99	23.02	31.12	0.99
	147	ADF, %DM	24.88	5.07	14.96	39.85	20.66	24.44	0.99
	149	ADL, %DM	4.87	1.2	2.6	8.58	3.2	4.8	0.91
	151	IVTD, %DM	54.41	7.03	37.91	70.18	41.7	53.33	0.99
	150	NDFD, %aNDF	85.61	4.56	72.07	93.13	82.6	85.69	0.78

CAL and VAL: Calibration data set and Test-set data set, respectively.

CP, aNDF, ADF, ADL, IVTD, NDFD: Crude protein, neutral detergent fiber with amylase treatment, Acid detergent fiber, Acid detergent lignin, *in vitro* true digestibility (48 h), and Neutral detergent fiber digestibility, respectively.

Table 5
Chemical composition statistics for Grass calibration (n = 399) and test-set (n = 117).

Set	N	Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Mode	Median	RSQ MAX
CAL	393	CP, %DM	18.86	4.14	9.66	34.55	15.35	18.39	1.00
	398	aNDF, %DM	54.65	5.32	39.03	68.18	51.78	54.98	0.99
	391	ADF, %DM	31.88	3.92	21.49	41.09	32.20	31.74	0.98
	398	ADL, %DM	3.49	0.78	1.85	6.12	2.80	3.43	0.79
	391	IVTD, %DM	86.13	5.10	70.65	95.82	79.84	86.41	0.98
	391	NDFD, %aNDF	75.20	7.23	54.63	91.16	66.48	75.40	0.91
VAL	117	CP, %DM	19.93	5.06	9.00	33.50	16.89	18.84	1.00
	117	aNDF, %DM	53.77	6.69	37.29	66.79	49.18	55.08	0.99
	115	ADF, %DM	31.39	5.68	20.33	44.57	26.62	32.76	0.99
	116	ADL, %DM	3.28	0.95	1.68	6.46	2.64	3.22	0.86
	117	IVTD, %DM	87.36	5.47	69.04	97.08	84.41	88.36	0.98
	117	NDFD, %aNDF	77.20	7.63	53.11	92.94	75.40	78.22	0.92

CAL and VAL: Calibration data set and Test-set data set, respectively.

CP, aNDF, ADF, ADL, IVTD, NDFD: Crude protein, neutral detergent fiber with amylase treatment, Acid detergent fiber, Acid detergent lignin, *In vitro* true digestibility (48 h), and Neutral detergent fiber digestibility, respectively.

Table 6
Pearson Correlation Coefficient between constituents for Alfalfa.

	CP	aNDF	ADF	ADL	IVTD	NDFD
CP	1					
aNDF	-0.63	1				
ADF	-0.42	0.93	1			
ADL	-0.48	0.91	0.9	1		
IVTD	0.55	-0.93	-0.9	-0.89	1	
NDFD	0.42	-0.73	-0.73	-0.73	0.92	1

All correlations are P < 0.01.

CP, aNDF, ADF, ADL, IVTD, NDFD: Crude protein, neutral detergent fiber with amylase treatment, Acid detergent fiber, Acid detergent lignin, *In vitro* true digestibility (48 h), and Neutral detergent fiber digestibility, respectively.

Table 7
Pearson Correlation Coefficient between constituents for Grasses.

	CP	aNDF	ADF	ADL	IVTD	NDFD
CP	1					
aNDF	-0.69	1				
ADF	-0.70	0.93	1			
ADL	-0.53	0.77	0.81	1		
IVTD	0.65	-0.87	-0.84	-0.8	1	
NDFD	0.61	-0.80	-0.78	-0.78	0.99	1

All correlations are P < 0.01.

CP, aNDF, ADF, ADL, IVTD, NDFD: Crude protein, neutral detergent fiber with amylase treatment, Acid detergent fiber, Acid detergent lignin, *In vitro* true digestibility (48 h), and Neutral detergent fiber digestibility, respectively.

derived by RSQcv, having values of 0.91 or greater with the only exception of IVTD with an RSQV of 0.71. The value of SECV was highest for NDFD (4.04% NDF), but for the other traits SECV were from 1.48% DM (NDFD) down to 0.33% DM for CP. Test-set performance had the expected small increase in predicting error (SEP) with a greater increase for CP and NDF. Nevertheless, performance in term of SEP and r^2_{val} were in line with the calibration performance. For both IVTD and NDFD, the slope was quite different from the ideal value of 1 which may be related to *in vitro* batch differences as *in vitro* digestions involve a biological process that varies with a different source of inoculum in each digestion run.

Performance of calibration of LABT for grasses (Table 9) were very similar to alfalfa in term of SECV, but with some differences in term of RPDcv in particular for ADL. In grasses the SECV for ADL were very similar to alfalfa (0.36 vs 0.33% DM), but the SD in grasses was only 0.78% DM with a RPD of only 2.17. This value is considered “poor” (Williams, 2014) compared to the RPDcv of alfalfa of 3.65 that had an SD of 5.18% DM. Nevertheless, ADL performance are quite good considering that for both forages the RSQcv was basically equal to the maximum RSQ (Table 4 and 5) obtainable, which would indicate that the real limit for ADL prediction with NIR is the reference method. Calibration performance for SEP were similar or even lower than SECV for NDF, ADL and NDFD, but about 20% higher for CP, ADF and IVTD.

In previous forage studies, SECV for NDF were between 1.76 and 2.74 % DM (Andueza et al., 2016; Brogna et al., 2009; Buxton and Mertens, 1991; Marten et al., 1983; Norris et al. 1976) compared to 1.11–1.19% DM of this study. Good performance were found also for ADF and ADL that had on average an SECV about 30 to 50% lower in

Table 8
Calibration and test-set performances for Alfalfa hay samples.

Calibration							Test-set				
Instrument	Parameter	PLS factors, n	SECV,%DM	RSQcv	SECV/SEL	RPDcv	r ² val	SEP	Slope	Bias	SEP/SECV
LAB	CP	9	0.62	0.97	2.93	6.24	0.93	1.14	1.06	-0.47	1.85
LAB	NDF	12	1.07	0.96	2.24	4.93	0.96	1.20	1.01	-0.47	1.13
LAB	ADF	11	1.01	0.96	1.75	4.85	0.93	1.34	1.03	-0.10	1.32
LAB	ADL	10	0.33	0.92	0.92	3.61	0.91	0.37	0.96	-0.05	1.11
LAB	IVTD	13	1.39	0.92	1.86	3.48	0.90	1.47	0.91	-0.08	1.05
LAB	NDFD	13	3.99	0.80	1.87	2.22	0.78	3.63	0.85	-0.96	0.91
LABT	CP	8	0.60	0.98	2.85	6.43	0.96	0.83	1.07	-0.29	1.39
LABT	NDF	10	1.11	0.96	2.34	4.73	0.95	1.49	1.01	-0.75	1.34
LABT	ADF	10	1.02	0.96	1.77	4.79	0.95	1.16	1.01	0.20	1.13
LABT	ADL	10	0.33	0.93	0.91	3.65	0.92	0.37	0.95	-0.13	1.13
LABT	IVTD	11	1.48	0.91	1.98	3.28	0.88	1.74	0.86	0.27	1.18
LABT	NDFD	11	4.04	0.79	1.90	2.19	0.74	4.24	0.74	-0.83	1.05
LABD	CP	9	0.66	0.97	3.15	5.81	0.89	1.31	1.09	-0.26	1.98
LABD	NDF	10	1.28	0.94	2.68	4.13	0.95	1.87	1.09	-1.36	1.47
LABD	ADF	11	1.07	0.95	1.84	4.60	0.94	1.29	1.09	-0.06	1.21
LABD	ADL	9	0.37	0.90	1.02	3.23	0.91	0.45	1.05	-0.28	1.22
LABD	IVTD	11	1.69	0.88	2.26	2.87	0.96	2.22	0.98	1.45	1.31
LABD	NDFD	10	4.72	0.72	2.21	1.88	0.67	5.14	0.78	2.72	1.09
DA	CP	5	0.63	0.97	3.00	6.11	0.90	1.23	1.09	-0.07	1.96
DA	NDF	9	1.21	0.95	2.55	4.35	0.96	1.64	1.06	-1.14	1.35
DA	ADF	9	0.96	0.96	1.66	5.10	0.94	1.25	1.05	0.23	1.30
DA	ADL	11	0.31	0.93	0.86	3.83	0.93	0.32	1.03	-0.02	1.02
DA	IVTD	9	1.51	0.90	2.03	3.20	0.92	1.51	0.89	0.50	1.00
DA	NDFD	9	4.15	0.78	1.95	2.13	0.93	4.50	0.70	-0.53	1.08
DLP	CP	10	0.92	0.94	4.36	4.20	0.85	1.52	1.11	0.32	1.66
DLP	NDF	11	1.55	0.91	3.25	3.40	0.92	2.21	1.07	-1.51	1.43
DLP	ADF	7	1.34	0.93	2.31	3.67	0.91	1.67	1.11	0.61	1.25
DLP	ADL	8	0.45	0.86	1.23	2.68	0.83	0.55	0.98	-0.25	1.23
DLP	IVTD	9	1.72	0.87	2.30	2.82	0.84	2.13	0.91	0.97	1.24
DLP	NDFD	9	4.55	0.74	2.14	1.95	0.54	5.62	0.64	0.91	1.24
LABS	CP	7	1.31	0.88	6.22	2.94	0.72	2.04	0.89	-0.29	1.56
LABS	NDF	7	2.43	0.79	5.11	2.17	0.68	3.16	1.03	0.12	1.30
LABS	ADF	8	2.41	0.76	4.16	2.04	0.59	3.72	0.94	1.81	1.55
LABS	ADL	6	0.66	0.70	1.81	1.83	0.55	0.81	0.92	-0.08	1.23
LABS	IVTD	6	2.63	0.70	3.52	1.84	0.62	2.82	1.01	0.14	1.07
LABS	NDFD	7	5.59	0.60	2.62	1.58	0.40	5.88	0.71	-1.38	1.05
SW	CP	5	1.55	0.84	7.36	2.49	0.65	2.38	0.82	0.59	1.54
SW	NDF	7	2.85	0.71	5.98	1.85	0.63	3.83	0.88	-1.72	1.35
SW	ADF	6	2.96	0.64	5.12	1.66	0.44	3.97	0.77	-0.67	1.34
SW	ADL	5	0.71	0.65	1.96	1.69	0.50	1.07	0.79	-0.61	1.50
SW	IVTD	7	2.87	0.65	3.84	1.69	0.64	3.32	0.80	1.65	1.16
SW	NDFD	6	6.23	0.51	2.92	1.42	0.59	5.48	0.80	2.78	0.88

LAB, LABT, LABD, DA, DLP, LABS, and SW: FOSS 6500, FOSS 6500 with 1100–2498 nm range, FOSS 6500 with 950–1650 nm range, AuroraNir, NIR-S-G1, FOSS 6500 with 740–1070 range, and SCiO, respectively.

magnitude of previous forage studies indicating a good quality of reference and spectral data of this study. Performance for CP of LABT showed an SECV of about 0.6–0.7% DM which is in line with the results of Andueza et al. (2016). The two (IVTD and NDFD) had the lowest RPD and highest SECV among forage traits for both forages. Even though SECV for IVTD is greater than the one for the other fiber fractions it is still much lower than what published in the literature (Brognna et al, 2009; Buxton and Mertens, 1991; Marten et al, 1983; Norris et al. 1976). There are very few published results for NDFD which is a relatively new parameter that is becoming increasingly popular, but it has been reported as having an intrinsically high laboratory error (Spanghero et al., 2010). Combining two forage quality traits (IVTD and NDF) for the calculation of NDFD reduced repeatability inflating NDFD SEL (Table 2). Large SEL have a direct effect on NIR calibration performance as shown in this study and by Lundberg et al. (2004) where reference variability is likely the main reason for lower prediction performance for NDFD.

The reference instrument LABT covered a spectral range of 1100–2498 nm collected with a PbS detector, but it was only a portion of the spectra of instrument LAB. With a spectral range of 400–2498 nm for LAB, LABT eliminates both the visible (400–780 nm) and short wave NIR (780–1098 nm) collected with a second Silicon detector. Despite the fact that LAB is covering a larger portion of the spectra, the performance of calibration were similar to the spectra trimmed LABT. This implies that

the extra spectra range for LAB did not provide much more information about chemical composition of samples compared to the trimmed LABT spectral range.

Removal of the upper portion of the spectral range (1652–2498 nm), however, influenced the LAB instrument, with LABD performance slightly worse than LABT. The increase in SECV for LABD was about 10% compared to LABT for both alfalfa and grasses indicating that by using a lower spectral range we likely lose information. Under test-set, LABD showed a greater increase in SEP for CP compared to SECV, but not for grasses that had a smaller (+15%) increase in SEP. In general, the good performance of calibration were confirmed also in test-set.

3.3.2. Portable instruments

Instruments DA and DLP covered the range 950–1650 nm that was matched by trimming LAB to LABD. Comparing RPDcv, DA had a very similar value to LABT for all traits in alfalfa (Table 8) but was slightly more variable for grasses (Table 9). SECV for alfalfa between DA and LABT were similar with grasses the values of SECV for DA were about 10% greater than LABT. In the case of DLP, however, there was a generalized decay of RPDcv values and an increase of SECV compared to either LABD or DA for both forages (Table 9). On average in grasses, SECV for DLP was about 50% greater than LABT, but it doubled for ADF and CP (Table 9). In alfalfa (Table 8), the SECV increase for DLP was

Table 9
Calibration and test-set performances for Grass hay samples.

Calibration							Test-set				
Instrument	Parameter	PLS factors, n	SECV,%DM	RSQcv	SECV/SEL	RPDcv	r ² val	SEP	Slope	Bias	SEP/SECV
LAB	CP	14	0.72	0.97	3.41	5.77	0.97	0.86	0.96	-0.03	1.20
LAB	NDF	9	1.14	0.95	2.39	4.68	0.98	1.17	0.93	0.47	0.94
LAB	ADF	14	0.63	0.97	1.01	6.19	0.98	0.93	1.03	0.32	1.39
LAB	ADL	10	0.37	0.78	1.01	2.13	0.80	0.45	0.85	-0.06	1.23
LAB	IVTD	8	1.69	0.89	2.26	3.01	0.89	2.43	0.77	0.64	1.38
LAB	NDFD	9	2.98	0.83	1.40	2.42	0.84	4.03	0.76	1.54	1.25
LABT	CP	12	0.72	0.97	3.41	5.78	0.97	0.93	0.95	-0.23	1.25
LABT	NDF	7	1.19	0.95	2.50	4.46	0.98	1.28	0.90	0.52	0.98
LABT	ADF	13	0.63	0.97	1.09	6.24	0.98	0.87	1.01	0.42	1.21
LABT	ADL	9	0.36	0.79	0.99	2.17	0.90	0.35	1.04	-0.18	0.82
LABT	IVTD	8	1.70	0.89	2.28	3.00	0.90	2.06	0.82	0.42	1.19
LABT	NDFD	7	3.20	0.80	1.50	2.26	0.87	3.16	0.90	1.37	0.89
LABD	CP	10	0.77	0.97	3.68	5.36	0.97	1.00	0.94	-0.44	1.15
LABD	NDF	5	1.38	0.93	2.89	3.86	0.95	1.53	0.96	0.28	1.09
LABD	ADF	11	0.71	0.97	1.22	5.53	0.98	0.94	1.02	3.89	1.20
LABD	ADL	9	0.38	0.76	1.05	2.04	0.85	0.40	0.98	-0.14	0.97
LABD	IVTD	5	2.00	0.85	2.68	2.55	0.84	2.32	0.86	-0.21	1.15
LABD	NDFD	5	3.59	0.75	1.68	2.01	0.77	3.87	0.86	-0.47	1.07
DA	CP	9	0.84	0.96	3.98	4.95	0.98	0.79	0.94	-0.01	0.95
DA	NDF	6	1.30	0.94	2.72	4.10	0.96	1.56	0.90	-0.18	1.19
DA	ADF	6	0.73	0.97	1.25	5.40	0.98	0.85	0.99	-0.07	1.17
DA	ADL	6	0.39	0.75	1.08	1.99	0.86	0.42	0.92	-0.19	0.93
DA	IVTD	5	1.87	0.87	2.50	2.73	0.86	2.35	0.83	-0.36	1.25
DA	NDFD	5	3.39	0.78	1.59	2.13	0.79	3.74	0.85	-0.81	1.08
DLP	CP	9	1.56	0.86	7.42	2.65	0.91	1.68	1.10	0.64	1.00
DLP	NDF	9	1.97	0.86	4.14	2.70	0.88	2.53	1.19	-0.37	1.27
DLP	ADF	10	1.39	0.88	2.40	2.83	0.92	1.90	1.22	-0.15	1.37
DLP	ADL	4	0.52	0.56	1.43	1.50	0.77	0.56	1.36	-0.24	1.02
DLP	IVTD	8	2.32	0.79	3.10	2.20	0.96	2.14	1.01	0.70	0.87
DLP	NDFD	5	4.06	0.69	1.91	1.78	0.80	3.90	1.07	1.92	0.84
LABS	CP	5	1.99	0.77	9.48	2.08	0.78	2.63	1.20	0.89	1.24
LABS	NDF	10	2.31	0.81	4.86	2.30	0.59	4.27	1.01	0.38	1.84
LABS	ADF	7	2.00	0.74	3.46	1.96	0.66	3.48	1.27	0.54	1.72
LABS	ADL	6	0.48	0.62	1.33	1.61	0.63	0.62	1.29	-0.16	1.25
LABS	IVTD	9	2.76	0.71	3.70	1.85	0.75	2.74	0.99	-0.23	0.99
LABS	NDFD	4	5.02	0.52	2.36	1.44	0.55	5.17	0.98	0.92	1.01
SW	CP	4	2.22	0.71	10.55	1.87	0.75	2.92	1.21	1.30	1.18
SW	NDF	5	2.96	0.69	6.22	1.80	0.72	3.60	1.00	-0.75	1.19
SW	ADF	4	2.42	0.62	4.19	1.62	0.77	3.10	1.36	-0.65	1.25
SW	ADL	3	0.56	0.48	1.55	1.39	0.60	0.69	1.45	-0.25	1.15
SW	IVTD	4	3.15	0.62	4.22	1.62	0.65	3.59	1.03	1.56	1.03
SW	NDFD	4	5.02	0.52	2.36	1.44	0.56	5.62	0.99	2.46	1.01

LAB, LABT, LABD, DA, DLP, LABS, and SW: FOSS 6500, FOSS 6500 with 1100–2498 nm range, FOSS 6500 with 950–1650 nm range, AuroraNir, NIR-S-G1, FOSS 6500 with 740–1070 range, and SCiO, respectively.

limited to about 20% for all traits. For alfalfa, SEPs with DA had a small increase for ADL, IVTD and NDFD compared to SECV, but for CP SEP was almost double the SECV. A similar effect was also recorded for LABD that would indicate that the upper NIR range 1650–2498 nm is important to maintain optimum accuracy for CP. As previously noted with the LABT test-set the DA and DLP slopes for NDFD were much smaller than the ideal value of 1. This was particularly evident for alfalfa test-set where the slope was (0.70 and 0.64) for DA and DLP, respectively. The consistency of this effect across all instruments and spectral ranges strongly indicate that the variation originates in the reference *in vitro* method.

Instrument SW covered the lower part of the spectral range in common only with the LABS instrument and overlapping with DA and DLP only between 950 and 1070 nm. With this instrument RPDcv for both forages were all below two, so they would be classified according to Williams (2014) as “Very poor”. The only exception was CP for alfalfa that had a RPDcv of 2.49, which would be good only for “Rough screening” (Williams, 2014). This is clearly shown in SECV, which was about double that for LABT about 70% higher than DA and 40% higher than DLP. Considering that there is a very high correlation (0.997) between SW and the LAB spectra trimmed to the same spectral range (LABS) it is not surprising that the performance of LABS also was considered “poor” (Williams, 2014) and only marginally better than SW. Instrument SW is a pocket size, low cost (less than 400 USD) NIR

spectrometer, that despite its low cost had spectra very well correlated to the spectra in the same spectral range of a much more expensive scanning monochromator laboratory instrument (LABT). However, performance showed that prediction does not have the accuracy needed for field or farm use.

The spectral NIR range is divided into combination and overtone bands (Workman, 1996) with decreasing absorption intensities going from the combination band (1900–2500 nm) down to the third overtone (700–1100 nm). The relative absorption intensity of the third overtone range (740–1050 nm) is about 100 times less than the first overtone (1500–2000 nm) and 10 times lower than second overtone (1050–1650 nm) spectral range (Workman, 1996). This is seen visually in Fig. 2, with several absorption peaks in the range 1100–2498 nm while the spectrum is relatively flat in the 740–1070 nm range for both SW and LABS. The main limitation of SW is that the scanning range misses the high absorption wavelengths where nutritional traits have a much higher signal. The fact that the third overtone range has less absorption allows the infrared light to travel and be transmitted more efficiently (Workman, 1996). This is well known by instrument manufacturers who use this spectral range for transmission instruments allowing them to increase absorption and have excellent performance for materials such as food and grain. However, when it is used in reflectance mode, as in the current study, the information that can be extracted from the NIR

spectrum is limited and predictive performance will typically be poor.

4. Conclusions

This study compared the prediction performance of three different portable instruments against a typical laboratory NIR instrument using alfalfa and grass forage samples. The differences in price across all instruments is huge. Costs range from (50–60,000 USD, LABT), (20–24,000 USD, DA), (6–10,000 USD, DLP), all the way down to (400 USD, SW). The laboratory instrument had the best performance as expected, and the very inexpensive instrument had much greater error of predictions to the point that, for most traits, the predictions were not reliable. The fact that both LABS and SW had similar poor performance, clearly indicates that NIR analysis in the spectral range of 700–1070 nm is not suited for forage quality determination regardless of spectrometer used. However, DA and DLP covering a more informative NIR range (950–1650 nm), with prices and performance intermediate between the two extremes, may provide a reasonable compromise and an alternative to the expensive laboratory equipment while still providing sufficiently accurate predictions. When choosing portable instruments, major attention should be placed to the spectral range covered and it should include second overtone (1050–1650 nm) and possibly first overtone (1500–2000 nm) with a combination band (1900–2500 nm) region. Again, this study was conducted using dried and ground preprocessed forage samples under typical laboratory conditions. Providing the instrument comparisons made in this study, there is potential in the future for portable instruments to be used beyond preprocessed samples for farm or field analysis fresh forages with less preparation and this option must be evaluated in future studies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

P. Berzaghi: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **J.H. Cherney:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **M.D. Casler:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing - review & editing, Resources.

Declaration of Competing Interest

Paolo Berzaghi is administrator of GraiNit srl, spin-off of the University of Padua, marketing AuroraNir spectrometer.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2021.106013>.

References

Andueza, D., Picard, F., Martin-Rosset, W., Aufrere, J., 2016. Near-infrared spectroscopy calibrations performed on oven-dried green forages for the prediction of chemical

- composition and nutritive value of preserved forage for ruminants. *Appl. Spec.* 70, 1321–1327. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0003702816654056>.
- AOAC, 1995. Protein (crude) in animal feed. Combustion method (990.03). In: Cunniff, P. (Ed.) Official methods of analysis of AOAC International. 15th ed. Locator no. 4.2.08. Assoc. of Official Analytical Chemists Int., Arlington, VA.
- Ball, D.M., Collins, M., Lacefield, G.D., Martin, N.P., Mertens, D.A., Olson, K.E., Putnam, D.H., Undersander, D.J., Wolf, M.W., 2001. Understanding Forage Quality. American Farm Bureau Federation Publication 1–01, Park Ridge, IL.
- Barnes, R.J., Dhanoa, M.S., Lister, S.J., 1989. Standard Normal Variate Transformation and DeTrending of Near Infrared Diffuse Reflectance Spectra. *Appl. Spectrosc.* 43 (5), 772–777. <https://doi.org/10.1366/0003702894202201>.
- Bec, K.B., Grabska, J., Siesler, H.W., Huck, C.W., 2020. Handheld near-infrared spectrometers: Where are we heading? *NIR News* 31 (3–4), 28–35. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0960336020916815>.
- Brogna, N., Pacchioli, M.T., Immovilli, A., Ruozi, F., Ward, R., Formigoni, A., 2009. The use of near-infrared reflectance spectroscopy (NIRS) in the prediction of chemical composition and *in vitro* neutral detergent fiber (NDF) digestibility of Italian alfalfa hay. *Ital. J. Anim. Sci.* 8 (Suppl. 2), 271–273.
- Buxton, D.R., Mertens, D.R., 1991. Errors in Forage-Quality Data Predicted by Near Infrared Reflectance Spectroscopy. *Crop Sci.* 31 (1), 212. <https://doi.org/10.2135/cropsci1991.0011183x00310001004>.
- Chen, L., Yang, Z., Han, L., 2013. A Review on the Use of Near-Infrared Spectroscopy for Analyzing Feed Protein Materials. *Appl. Spec. Rev.* 48 (7), 509–522. <https://doi.org/10.1080/05704928.2012.756403>.
- Dairyland Laboratories, 2020. <https://www.dairylandlabs.com/resources/feedandforage/summaries> (accessed on April 10th).
- Esteve Agelet, L., Hurburgh, C., 2010. A Tutorial on Near Infrared Spectroscopy and Its Calibration. *Crit. Rev. Anal. Chem.* 40, 246–260. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408347.2010.515468>.
- Fearn, T., 2005. Calculating standard deviations. *NIR News* 16 (5).
- Lundberg, K.M., Hoffman, P.C., Bauman, L.M., Berzaghi, P., 2004. Prediction of forage energy content by near infrared reflectance spectroscopy and summative equations. *Profession. Anim. Scient.* 20 (3) [https://doi.org/10.15232/S1080-7446\(15\)31309-7](https://doi.org/10.15232/S1080-7446(15)31309-7).
- Marten, G.C., Halgerson, J.L., Cherney, J.H., 1983. Quality prediction of small grain silage forages by near infrared reflectance spectroscopy. *Crop Sci.* 23, 94–96.
- Norris, K.H., Barnes, R.F., Moore, J.E., Shenk, J.S., 1976. Predicting Forage Quality by Infrared Reflectance Spectroscopy. *J. Animal Sci.* 43 (4), 889–897. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas1976.434889x>.
- Paz, C. C. D., A., A. G. M. E. Silva, and A. C. D. Rego. 2019. Use of near infrared spectroscopy for the evaluation of forage for ruminants. *Rev. Cienc. Agrar.* 62, doi: 10.22491/rca.2019.2923.
- SAS Institute, 2017. SAS add in for Microsoft Excel. Version 7.15. SAS Inst. Inc., Cary, NC.
- Spanghero, M., Berzaghi, P., Fortina, R., Masoero, F., Rapetti, L., Zanfi, C., Tassone, S., Gallo, A., Colombini, S., Ferlito, J.C., 2010. Technical note: Precision and accuracy of *in vitro* digestion of neutral detergent fiber and predicted net energy of lactation content of fibrous feeds. *J. Dairy Sci.* 93, 4855–4859. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2010-3098>.
- Sparkfun Website, 2020. <https://learn.sparkfun.com/tutorials/scio-pocket-molecular-scanner-teardown-/all#optical-sensor-teardown> (accessed on April 24th).
- St-Pierre, N.R., Cobanov, B., 2007. A model to determine the optimal sampling schedule of diet components. *J. Dairy Sci.* 90, 5383–5394. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2006-727>.
- St-Pierre, N.R., Weiss, W.P., 2015. Partitioning variation in nutrient composition data of common feeds and mixed diets on commercial dairy farms. *J. Dairy Sci.* 98, 5004–5015. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2015-9431>.
- Valentine, M.E., Karayilanli, E., Cherney, J.H., Cherney, D.J., 2019. Comparison of *in vitro* long digestion methods and digestion rates for diverse forages. *Crop Sci.* 58, 114.
- Yan, H., Siesler, H.W., 2018. Hand-held near-infrared spectrometers: State-of-the-art instrumentation and practical applications. *NIR News* 2018 (29), 8–12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0960336018796391>.
- Weiss W.P., Shoemaker, D.E., McBeth, L.R., Yoder, P.S., St-Pierre, N.R., 2012. Within-farm variation in nutrient composition of feeds. *Proc. Tri-State Dairy Nutr. Conf., Ft. Wayne, IN.* Ohio State University, Columbus, pp. 103–140.
- Williams, P., 2014. The RPD statistic: A tutorial note". *NIR news* 25 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1255/nirn.1419>.
- Williams, P., Dardenne, P., Flinn, P., 2017. Tutorial: Items to be included in a report on a near infrared spectroscopy project. *JNIRS* 25 (2), 85–90.
- Workman Jr., J.J., 1996. Interpretive Spectroscopy for Near Infrared. *J. Appl. Spectroscopy Rev.* 31 (3).